

Zeynep Derya Tarman, LL.D.,*
Full Professor,
Koç University Law School,

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Ceyda Süral Efeçınar, LL.D.,**
Full Professor,
Piri Reis University Law School,
Republic of Turkey

EVALUATION OF TURKISH COURT PRACTICE REGARDING THE HAGUE CONVENTION ON CHILD ABDUCTION

Abstract: *The Convention of 25 October 1980 on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction ("Convention") aims to secure prompt return of children who were wrongfully removed to, or retained in a Contracting State, in violation of the rights of custody or access under the law of another Contracting State. However, it is possible to refuse the return of the child. The reasons for the refusal of return are set out in Articles 12, 13 and 20 of the Convention. Among these, the most frequently invoked exception is stipulated under Article 13/1-b, often called as the "grave risk" exception. Türkiye is a party to the Convention as of 2000. In the twenty-three years following its entry into force, there is a high volume of Turkish case-law related with the Convention as Turkish citizens historically tend to form cross-border families especially within Europe. In our paper, the recent Turkish court decisions are reviewed and Turkish court practice is evaluated in light of two very recent sources published by the Hague Conference on Private International Law; Guide to Good Practice 2020 on Article 13/1-b, and Conclusions and Recommendations by the Eighth Meeting of the Special Commission dated October 2023. How the Turkish courts construe "habitual residence" of the child; the importance given to hearing of the child and his/her opinion in invoking the "child's objection" as a separate ground for refusal; and certain problems in implementation of "grave risk" exception are especially set forth, and conclusions as to Turkish practice are drawn.*

* ztarman@ku.edu.tr

** csural@pirireis.edu.tr

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1. Introduction

The Convention of 25 October 1980 on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction (“Convention” or “Hague Convention”) is an international treaty that provides a civil remedy to parents seeking the return of a child wrongfully removed or retained across international borders. The Convention is based on an assumption that it is harmful to children to be unilaterally taken from their country of habitual residence, and seeks to deter such actions.

The Convention applies to children under 16 years of age who have their habitual residence in a Contracting State if they have been wrongfully removed by their parents¹ to another Contracting State or retained in a Contracting State which is not their habitual residence. The purpose of the Convention is to ensure that a child who has been wrongfully “removed” or “retained” within the meaning of the Convention is returned as soon as possible to the Contracting State of habitual residence.

In order for the Convention to apply, both countries (the one the child was removed from, and the one the child has been brought to) must be “Contracting States”, i.e. both must have adopted the Convention.

Turkey is a party to the Hague Convention since 2000. The Convention has 103 State Parties, including the United States of America, Australia, Canada, Russia, and many European countries such as Albania, Bosnia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Germany, Greece, Montenegro, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Serbia. Therefore, the Convention is applied widely in Türkiye and there is a mass amount of case-law and doctrine.

Turkey has enacted a law on the procedures and principles regarding the implementation of the Convention: Law No. 5717, “Law on the Legal Aspects and Scope of International Child Abduction”. Additionally, the Circular No. 65/2 is issued by the Ministry of Justice in accordance with this Law. These serve as a guideline for the judges and practitioners.²

¹ The Convention can be applied not only if the child is abducted by the mother or father, but also if the child is abducted by persons such as grandparents who are likely to have custody rights in the future. Giray, F. K, *Milletlerarası Özel Hukukta Kaçırılan veya Alıkonan Çocukların İadesi*, İstanbul: Beta Yayıncılık, 2010, p.27.

² For a Turkish summary of the Convention and its implementation in Türkiye, see, Özdemir, F B, *Uluslararası Çocuk Kaçırma ve Kaçırılan Çocukların İadesi*, Marmara Üniversitesi Hukuk

Recently, the Hague Conference issued two publications concerning the Convention. In 2020, the Guide to Good Practice on Article 13/1/b³ ("Guide to Good Practice") and the Conclusions and Recommendations of the Eighth Meeting of the Special Commission ("Special Commission Report") on the practical operation of the Convention held in October 2023.⁴

In this paper, we aim to evaluate recent case-law of the Turkish courts concerning the Convention especially in the light of recent materials published by the Hague Conference.

2. Conditions for the Applicability of the Hague Convention

The purpose of the Convention is to secure the return of the child who has been displaced wrongfully to a Contracting State as soon as possible and to ensure the rights of custody and of access under the law of a Contracting State are effectively respected in the other Contracting States.

The conditions required for the Convention to be applicable can be listed as follows:

The applicant had custody rights that were infringed by the alleged removal or retention,

The applicant essentially was exercising his/her custody rights at time of removal or retention,

The applicant was habitually resident in a Contracting State at the time of the removal or retention,

The abducted child has not yet reached the age of 16.⁵

If all these conditions are fulfilled, the person who has custody rights of the child may request the return of the child to the country of his/her habitual residence within the framework of the Convention.

Fakültesi Hukuk Araştırmaları Dergisi, 25(2), 2019, pp. 1164-1189.

³ <https://www.hcch.net/en/news-archive/details/?varevent=725>

⁴ <https://www.hcch.net/en/publications-and-studies/details4/?pid=8488>

⁵ For opinions on the moment to be taken as basis in terms of the condition that the child has not reached the age of sixteen see Giray 210, op. cit., p. 32 ff. The 2nd Civil Chamber of the Court of Cassation, in its decision numbered E.2006/17627-K.2007/12722 and dated 27.09.2007, ruled that the child could not be returned since the child was 16 years old at the time of the return request and that the child was outside the scope of the Convention in accordance with Article 4 of the Convention. In its decision dated 13.11.2013 and numbered E.2013/2-1772-K.2013/1557, the Court of Cassation General Assembly of Civil Chambers ruled that "... Onur, one of the children whose return is requested, was born on 27.04.1996 and has reached the age of 16 as of the date of the examination and has left the scope of the Convention in accordance with Article 4 of the Convention."

2.1. Infringement of Custody Rights

It is important to note that, in order for the Convention to be applicable, it is not necessary for there to be a judicial or administrative decision concerning the right of custody between the child and the parent requesting the return. The fact that the right of custody has arisen by law is sufficient for the return of the child under the provisions of the Convention (Art. 3).⁶

As a matter of fact, this point is clearly emphasized in the decision of the 2nd Civil Chamber of the Court of Cassation dated 27.9.2007 and numbered E.2006/17627-K.2007/12722. The relevant part of the judgment is as following: “According to the Child Abduction Convention, it is not necessary to have a decision on custody or the right to establish personal relations taken by the authorities of the country of habitual residence of the child who is wrongfully taken from one contracting state to another or wrongfully retained in the country of the other contracting state, nor is there any obligation to recognize and enforce such a decision in the state where the child is wrongfully taken or wrongfully retained.”

2.2. Habitual Residence

In determining whether the conditions for the application of the Convention have been fulfilled, the country of habitual residence of the child is of great importance. Whether the child has been wrongfully relocated or retained cannot be determined without determining the child’s habitual residence.

The Convention does not define the term “habitual residence”, so it is open to the courts in each Contracting State to do so. It is intended to be a fact-based determination, avoiding legal technicalities. The issue of how to determine the habitual residence of the child is highly discussed in the doctrine⁷ and in practice. Although there is not a binding definition on habitual residence, in international doctrine and court practices, there is an understanding that is accepted as the definition of habitual residence.⁸ It is important to note here that when determining the habitual residence of the child, it is not correct to interpret the country in which the child has lived for more days as the habitual residence. In other words, the child’s place of residence should not be determined solely on the basis of finger counting,⁹ and the

⁶ Giray, 2010, *op. cit.*, p. 91.

⁷ For opinions on the determination of the habitual residence of the child see Giray, 2010, *op. cit.*, p. 74; Akıncı, Z., Demir Gökyayla, C, *Milletlerarası Aile Hukuku*. Ankara, 2010, p. 215; Çelikel, A., Erdem, B., *Milletlerarası Özel Hukuk*, İstanbul, 2020, p. 299-300.

⁸ Akıncı/Demir Gökyayla, *op. cit.*, p. 215.

⁹ Çelikel/Erdem, *op. cit.*, p. 300.

child's age and maturity should also be taken into consideration, and it should be examined whether the child maintains social life relationships and adapts to the environment in which he/she currently lives¹⁰.

According to case law, "*in determining the habitual residence within the meaning of Article 4 of the Convention, only the child shall be taken as a basis and it shall be examined where he/she established his/her social environment and continued his/her social life in the days immediately preceding the date of the alleged abduction or retention, and if the child who is the subject of the return case is a minor and therefore lives dependent on his/her mother, the habitual residence of the mother and the habitual residence of the child shall be the same place on the date immediately preceding the date of the abduction or retention.*"¹¹

An interesting example was brought before Istanbul Civil Court of Appeal,¹² where the child, who was born in 2013 in Turkey, was brought to Turkey by his parents in 2016. The mother refused to leave Turkey and the child was requested to be returned to USA by his father. It is determined by the Court that due to numerous change of jobs by his father, the child lived in Moscow, Vienna, New York and Atlanta since his birth. As he was born in Turkey, lived in different countries and cities since his birth and at an age still in need of his mother, his habitual residence was not accepted as to be in USA but in Turkey.

In another case before Antalya Civil Court of Appeal,¹³ the child was born in 2014 in Sweden. He was brought to Turkey when he was 3 months old and mostly stayed with his father's family in Turkey. The court concluded that the child is habitually resident in Turkey, not in Sweden and denied his return to Sweden.

3. Return Procedure and the Role of Central Authorities

The initiation of the return process under the provisions of the Convention depends primarily on the filing of a return request. The mechanism established by the Convention ensures that the request for the return of the child can be made easily and that this request can be evaluated and finalized quickly.¹⁴

¹⁰ Şanlı, C., Esen, E., Ataman – Figanmeşe, İ., Milletlerarası Özel Hukuk, İstanbul, 2021, p.204.

¹¹ Court of Cassation General Assembly of Civil Chambers, dated 22.10.2010 and numbered E.2010/2-628-K.2010/693.

¹² İstanbul Civil Court of Appeal, 10th Civil Chamber, E. 2018/1708 K. 2018/965 T. 3.7.2018.

¹³ Antalya Civil Court of Appeal, 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2020/1870 K. 2020/1661 T. 20.11.2020.

¹⁴ Akıncı/Demir -Gökyayla, *op. cit.*, p. 246.

The Convention requires each Contracting State to designate a so-called “*central authority*” for the return mechanism to function. The central authority is the office or person through which each country carries out its duties under the Convention. Under the Convention, the central authorities have direct contact with each other and act in co-operation for the return of the child. The central authority designated by Turkey under the Convention is the Directorate General for Foreign Relations and European Union within the Ministry of Justice.

The person requesting the return of the abducted child may submit an application for the return of the child to the central authority of any Contracting State (Art. 8). The Convention thus relieves the person requesting the return of the child from the burden of travelling to the Contracting State where the child was abducted and applying for return to the authorities of that State. The person requesting the return of the child may apply to the central authority of the Contracting State in which he/she is resident and request the return of the child. For instance, if a child whose habitual residence is in Turkey is abducted to a foreign Contracting State, the application for the return of the child may be made to the Chief Public Prosecutor’s Office of the place where the child’s habitual residence is in Turkey [Circular No. 65/2, Art. II (A)(2)]. Moreover, under the Convention, central authorities may not charge any costs for applications submitted to them [Art. 26(2)].¹⁵

The central authority receiving the request for the return of the child shall promptly forward it to the central authority of the Contracting State to which the child was taken (or retained) by abduction. When the central authority of the Contracting State to which the child has been abducted or retained receives the request for the return of the child, it shall, if necessary, attempt to locate the child. In practice, the abductor conceals the child in order to prevent the return of the child, and therefore it may be difficult to locate the child, even with the assistance of police authorities. Once the child has been located, this central authority shall attempt to secure the return of the child by persuading the abductor [Art. 7(c)].¹⁶ If the abductor cannot be persuaded to return the child, the central authority of the country to which the child was abducted shall apply to the competent judicial or administrative authority of that country for a decision on the return of the child [Art. 7(f)]. In the case of children who have been abducted to Turkey, an applica-

¹⁵ Şanlı/Esen/Ataman – Figanmeşe, p.205.

¹⁶ For mediation practice in child abduction cases see Öztekin – Gelgel, G, 25 Ekim 1980 Tarihli Uluslararası Çocuk Kaçırma ve Hukuki Yönlerine İlişkin Lahey Sözleşmesi Çerçevesinde Arabuluculuk Uygulaması, Public and Private International Law Bulletin, 37 (2), 2017, pp. 621.

tion shall be made to the Family Courts¹⁷ for a decision on the return of the child (Law No. 5717, Art. 6).¹⁸

The judicial or administrative authority to which the application is made must decide on the return of the child immediately. This authority shall only decide whether or not to return the child; it shall not decide on custody. The Convention does not decide which parent should have guardianship or custody of the child. Instead, it leaves that decision to the country of the child's habitual residence, if the child is ordered to be returned.

Decisions on a request for return may be appealed.¹⁹ In accordance with the Convention, when a decision is finalized to return a child, it must be executed immediately, and the child shall be returned. In the case of children who have been abducted to Turkey, if the child is not returned despite the return order of the Family Court, the order shall be enforced by force.²⁰

4. Denial of Return of the Child to His/Her Habitual Residence

The Convention relates to judicial cooperation and, as a rule, the child should be returned immediately to the habitual residence. However, it is possible to refuse the return, although it is exceptional. Situations that prevent the return of the child are stated in an extremely limited manner in the Convention. The Convention sought to prevent the courts from confusing the return mechanism with the decision on the child's custody by preventing them from investigating the best interests of the child in general.²¹ The reasons for the refusal of return are set out in the articles 12, 13 and 20 of

¹⁷ The 2nd Civil Chamber of the Court of Cassation, in its decision numbered E.2007/17942-K.2007/16493 and dated 26.11.2007, stated that the family courts are competent in the cases arising from the Convention, and found it contrary to the procedure and the law to decide on the merits of the case while the domestic court should have made a decision of lack of competence.

¹⁸ Şanlı/Esen/Ataman Figanmeşe *op. cit.*, p.206.

¹⁹ In its decision numbered E.2014/2-1518-K.2014/844 and dated 05.11.2014, the Court of Cassation General Assembly of Civil Chambers concluded that the Chief Public Prosecutor's Office, which filed a return case on behalf of the central authority, should also request an appeal on behalf of the central authority when appealing the decision rendered in the return case, and that the appeal request not submitted on behalf of the central authority is invalid; and that the appeal request submitted by the Dutch lawyer working in a law office in the Netherlands on behalf of the mother requesting the return of the child should be rejected on the grounds that the foreign lawyer does not have the authority to represent and therefore appeal the judgment in this case in accordance with Article 35(1) of the Attorneys' Act No. 1136.

²⁰ Akıncı/Demir Gökyayla, *op. cit.*, p. 272.

²¹ *Ibid.*, p. 281.

the Convention. These may be listed as follows:²²

Consent to or subsequent acquiescence²³ to the removal or retention, (Art. 12)

The custody right was not being effectively exercised (Art. 13/1/a)

Grave risk of physical or psychological harm to the child in case of return (Art. 13/1/b)

Child's objection to being returned if he/she is at a sufficient age and degree of maturity (Art. 13/2)

Breach of fundamental principles of the requested State relating to the protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms (Art. 20)

If the period from the wrongful removal or retention of the child to the date of receipt of the application to the judicial or administrative authorities of the contracting state exceeds one year, the court may reject the request for the return of the child, in addition to the reasons listed above, on the grounds that "the child has adapted to his/her new environment" (Art. 12).²⁴ Absence of application within one year following the wrongful removal or retention of the child is not a time limit that violates rights. However, the passage of this one-year period will play an important role in the evaluation of the extradition request.²⁵

In deciding the return of the children to their habitual residence, there are two issues which are of significance in recent court practice. One is sufficient level of scrutiny; i.e. whether the court conducts satisfactory examination in determining the existence of these grounds, or refrains from a thorough examination for the sake of a rapid decision. Second issue is whether the young age of the child obliges the court to return the child to his/her mother. Among the grounds for denial of return, most applied and discussed are child's objection and grave risk of harm to the child. Therefore, these will be further explained with case-law examples below.

²² In its decision dated 13.11.2013 and numbered E.2013/2-1772, K.2013/1557, the Court of Cassation General Assembly of Civil Chambers ruled that any of the reasons for refraining from return listed in Articles 13 and 20 of the Child Abduction Convention are sufficient for the rejection of the return application independently and that the court examining the return application should examine these exceptions *ex officio*.

²³ The time elapsed from the date of abduction to the date of receipt of the application for the return of the child by the competent judicial or administrative authorities of the country to which the child was abducted is of importance for the decision on the return of the child [Art. 12 (1)]. The request of return shall be made within one year from the date of removal or retention, otherwise, it may mean that there is subsequent acquiescence or that the child is settled in his/her new environment.

²⁴ Şanlı/Esen/Ataman – Figanmeşe, *op. cit.*, p.209.

²⁵ Akıncı/Demir Gökyayla, *op. cit.*, p. 209.

4.1. Sufficient Level of Scrutiny

While the purpose of the Convention is to ensure prompt return of the child to his/her habitual residence, allegations that there is a ground for non-return should be carefully examined. This is stated in the Guide to Good Practice as follows: “*the exceptions serve a legitimate purpose, as the Convention does not contemplate an automatic return mechanism. ... This means that while the purpose of the Convention is to address the harmful effects of international child abduction by ensuring the prompt return of the child to the State of habitual residence where any custody / access and related issues should be resolved, there may be exceptional circumstances allowing for the non-return of the child.*” (paras. 27-28).

As a matter of fact, many decisions of Turkish family courts of first instance are annulled by the Court of Cassation due to lack of sufficient scrutiny of the alleged claims of relevant parties.

For example, the decision of a family court to return children to Austria was annulled because it was given without inviting the father taking the children to Turkey to the hearings; thus without examining any evidence that could have been submitted by the father; without hearing the children and without taking the opinion of experts.²⁶

Another decision of a family court was annulled because it did not refer to an expert report from a panel comprising of a psychologist, a pedagogue and a social worker on the possible effects of return to the child.²⁷

In another case before the Court of Cassation, a law suit had been initiated against the father before a Turkish criminal court accusing him of sexual harassment towards the child where the father had not been condemned because of lack of sufficient proof. Nevertheless, the family court decided to return the child to this father but the Court of Cassation annulled the decision of the family court on the ground that the case file decided by the criminal court had not been requested nor reviewed by the family court.²⁸

4.2. Young Age of the Child

Until 2012, it was widely accepted by the Turkish courts that young age of the child may constitute a sole reason for the child not to be separated from his/her mother. However, in *Ilker Ensar Uyanık v. Turkey*²⁹ case,

²⁶ Samsun Civil Court of Appeal, 4th Civil Chamber, E. 2018/210 K. 2018/1228 T. 23.5.2018.

²⁷ Court of Cassation 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2021/8603 K. 2021/7898 T. 1.11.2021.

²⁸ Court of Cassation, 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2022/1492 K. 2022/2946 T. 28.3.2022.

²⁹ *Ilker Ensar Uyanık v. Turkey*, no. 60328/09, 3.5.2012. See, Giray, F. K, *Avrupa İnsan Hakları*

the European Court of Human Rights (“ECHR”) decided that although there is no doubt that a child’s very young age is an important criterion in determining his/her interests, it could not in itself be a sufficient ground in denying the return of the child.³⁰

Therefore, recent decisions of the Court of Cassation are in line with this judgment. Although, family courts of first instance still decide to deny return of the child solely based on his/her young age, such decisions are consistently annulled by the Court of Cassation.³¹

4.3. Grounds for Denial of Return of the Child to His/Her Habitual Residence

4.3.1. Child’s objection to being returned

According to the Hague Convention Art. 13/II, “*The judicial or administrative authority may also refuse to order the return of the child if it finds that the child objects to being returned and has attained an age and degree of maturity at which it is appropriate to take account of its views.*”

It is noted in the Special Commission Report “*that the ‘child objection’ exception under Article 13(2) of the 1980 Child Abduction Convention is separate from Article 13(1)(b)*” (para. 38).

Furthermore, Turkey is a party to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. According to Article 12 of the UN Convention, “*States Parties shall assure to the child who is capable of forming his or her own views the right to express those views freely in all matters affecting the child*”.³²

Indeed, statements of the child are heard and taken into consideration in Turkish court practice and they may constitute a sole basis for denial of return.³³ It is also crucial for decisive authorities to bear in mind that the

Mahkemesinin Aile İçi Uluslararası Çocuk Kaçırma İhtilaflarına İlişkin Seçilmiş Kararları, Public and Private International Law Bulletin. 35 (2), 2015, pp. 195-197.

³⁰ Akıncı/Demir Gökyayla, *op. cit.*, p. 287.

³¹ Court of Cassation 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2021/3172 K. 2021/3190 T. 19.4.2021; Court of Cassation 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2021/5111 K. 2021/5698 T. 5.7.2021.

³² Art. 12 : “1. *States Parties shall assure to the child who is capable of forming his or her own views the right to express those views freely in all matters affecting the child, the views of the child being given due weight in accordance with the age and maturity of the child. 2. For this purpose, the child shall in particular be provided the opportunity to be heard in any judicial and administrative proceedings affecting the child, either directly, or through a representative or an appropriate body, in a manner consistent with the procedural rules of national law.*”

³³ In its decision numbered E.2013/2-1772-K.2013/1557 and dated 13.11.2013, the Court of Cassation General Assembly of Civil Chambers concluded that the child, born in 1999,

party wrongfully takes away the child can manipulate the child's feelings by fulfilling all the child's wishes until the process for return is completed³⁴. Certain examples may be given from recent case-law. In a case before Izmir Civil Court of Appeal, the child was born in 2009 in the Netherlands. He came to Turkey in 2018 with his father and did not go back to the Netherlands. Although, there are not any reasons for denial of return of the child, the Court denied his return, taking into consideration the statements of the child before an expert and before the judge where he talked about his problems about living in the Netherlands with his mother; and where he stated that he is happy and he wants to continue living his father in Turkey. The Court based its decision on Art. 12 of the UN Convention as the child is 11 years old, a student of fourth grade at elementary school; so, he is mature enough to be heard and to affect the decision of the judicial authorities in matters relating to his life.³⁵

In another case before Kayseri Civil Court of Appeal, the child, born in 2012 in Germany, was brought to Turkey by her mother when she was 8 years old. She testified before a panel of experts and before the judge where she stated that she didn't want to go back to Germany; she wanted to stay with her mother and that her father used to beat her mother in her presence while they had been in Germany. Although there were no other reasons for denial of return, the Court decided to deny the child's return based on Art. 13/II as the child is at a sufficient age and degree of maturity to take her views into account.³⁶

However, if the statements of the child are inconsistent and there are other facts to prove to the contrary, Turkish courts decide opposite of the child's statement. For example, in a case before Sakarya Civil Court of Appeal, two children, born in 2009 and 2011 in the Netherlands, were brought to Turkey by their father in 2017. During the procedure for their return initiated by their mother, children were heard by experts and they stated that they wanted to stay with their father in Turkey. However, the experts noticed that the children missed their mother and they were not settled in their new envi-

whose return was requested, was capable of forming his/her opinions independently of his/her parents due to his/her age at the time of the hearing, and that the child stated that he/she wanted to stay with his/her mother in Türkiye, and since it could not be proved that staying with his/her mother was contrary to the principle of the best interests of the child, the request for return of the child should be rejected.

³⁴ Özel, S., Erkan, M., Pürselim, H. S., Karaca, H. A, Milletlerarası Özel Hukuk, İstanbul, 2023, p. 294.

³⁵ İzmir Civil Court of Appeal, 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2020/1609 K. 2020/1754 T. 25.12.2020.

³⁶ Kayseri Civil Court of Appeal, 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2020/741 K. 2020/622 T. 22.9.2020.

ronment in Turkey. Furthermore, the director of the elementary school was heard and stated that although the children were registered at their school, they didn't regularly attend the classes. So, the Court decided on the return of children to Netherlands contrary to their statements.³⁷

4.3.2 Grave Risk of Harm to the Child

Article 13(b), which provides the most frequently cited defense available under the Convention, stipulates that a court is not required to order the return of a child to his or her state of habitual residence if “*there is a grave risk that his or her return would expose the child to physical or psychological harm.*”

This ground has been discussed frequently also by the Turkish courts since the entry into force of the Convention.³⁸ Below, we will give examples from recent case-law especially in the light of the Guide to Good Practice.

General considerations such as age of the child, reaching puberty, need of a mother, possibility of negative effects on the child if he/she is taken away from his/her mother are not construed as grave risks.³⁹ Also, in a very recent case from 2023, the father's claim that the children are under a grave risk of harm because the mother is living with her boyfriend in Austria has been rejected and the children are returned to Austria.⁴⁰

On the other hand, an ongoing war is deemed to constitute a reason for grave risk of harm. In the case before the Court of Cassation, the mother's request of return was denied on the ground of grave risk of harm first because of the ongoing war in Ukraine⁴¹. However, it must be noted that a country's being constantly in conflict or having certain security issues is not sufficient for denial of return as in the case of Israel in the beginning of 2000s. In the decision of the Sarıyer Family Court numbered E.2004/683-K.2004/929 and dated 25.10.2004, which was upheld by the decision of the 2nd Civil Chamber of the Court of Cassation numbered E.2005/469-K.2005/5045 and dated 29.3.2005, the interpretation of the Sarıyer Family Court within the framework of Article 13(b) of the Convention upon the opposition to the request

³⁷ Sakarya Civil Court of Appeal, 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2019/36 K. 2019/35 T. 21.1.2019.

³⁸ For further information, see, Saatçioğlu, O C, *Uluslararası Çocuk Kaçırmanın Hukuki Veçheleri Hakkında Sözleşme Madde 13/1-b Hükmü Kapsamında “Ev İçi Şiddet” Olgusu: Eleştirel Bir Değerlendirme*, Public and Private International Law Bulletin, 41(1), 2021, pp. 1–40.

³⁹ Court of Cassation 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2022/7603 K. 2022/6922 T. 12.9.2022.

⁴⁰ Court of Cassation 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2022/11535 K. 2023/694 T. 23.2.2023.

⁴¹ Court of Cassation 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2023/2327 K. 2023/1264 T. 23.3.2023. Furthermore, in this case, the child had been attacked and severely injured by a nephew of the mother in Ukraine.

for the return of the child to Israel on the grounds of security issues in Israel was as follows: *“Lastly, the objection of the defendant’s attorney based on Article 13/b of the Convention that the conditions for return are not met due to the war environment in Israel, and the objection of the defendant’s attorney that the normal daily life such as education, training, trade, travelling and so on is still continuing in Israel, that the disorder and conflicts in the country are in certain regions, and that these conflicts are not a new situation but have been going on for many years and that the parties have continued their lives in Israel despite this, these objections have not been deemed appropriate. Furthermore, it has not been proved that there is a grave risk that the return of the child would expose him/her to physical or psychological danger or otherwise put him/her in an intolerable situation, and it is understood that there is no reason for refusal stated in this article”.*

There are two interesting recent examples where the child’s return has been denied. First example concerns health condition of one of the siblings. In a case before Ankara Civil Court of Appeal, two children, born in 2013 and 2015, were brought from Austria to Turkey. One of these children was diagnosed with osteoporosis (loss of bones) and should be under strict treatment. The return of children was denied because *“Turkey’s health system is superior to that of many European countries and many foreign patients prefer to be treated in Turkish hospitals”* and *“the mother, being an housewife, can spend more time with and better take care of the sick child”*⁴². The risks associated with the child’s health have been dealt with in the Guide to Good Practice. It is stated that *“In cases involving assertions associated with the child’s health, the grave risk analysis usually should focus on the availability of treatment in the State of habitual residence of the child and not on a comparison between the relative quality of care in each State”* (para. 62). Therefore, we see that Turkish court’s decision clearly conflicts with the Guide because the court made a comparison between health systems and furthermore the comparison depends not on an objective scientific document but on the probably subjective opinion of the Turkish judge.

Second example concerns separation of siblings, an issue also dealt with in the Guide to Good Practice. In a case before Sakarya Civil Court of Appeal, the child, born in 2017 in Austria, was brought to Turkey by her mother in 2018. The father frequently visits his family and the couple had another child in 2018 who is born in Turkey. After the birth of the second child, the father requests the return of the first child. The court denies his return on the ground of grave risks which are the young age of the child, his need of

⁴² Ankara Civil Court of Appeal, 1st Civil Chamber., E. 2018/3184 K. 2019/275 T. 5.3.2019.

his mother's care, busy working hours of the father in Austria, and the possible psychological harm on the child if he is separated from his mother and his newborn brother.⁴³ However, it is stated in the Guide that *"In some cases, a separation of siblings may be difficult and disruptive for each child. ... the separation of the siblings resulting from the non-return of one child (regardless of the legal basis for the non-return) does not usually result in a grave risk determination for the other child"* (para. 74). Although certain other grounds are cited as grave risks in the decision, they are general considerations not accepted by Turkish courts and it is obvious that the determinant factor was the separation of siblings in denial of return.

It is stated by the Hague Conference in the Special Commission Report that the interpretation and application of the exceptions shall *"not include a comprehensive 'best interests assessment'"* (para. 17). However, these two case-law examples show that the grave risk exception is not being applied as restrictively as expected.

5. Conclusion

It is very important that the central authorities and the officials assisting these authorities correctly understand the nature of the duty assigned to them by the Convention. The Convention is certainly not of a criminal nature and is not a Convention that foresees punishment for the party who wrongfully removes or retains the child. The duty of the central authority is, first, to mediate for the return of the child, and after the child is found, to try to persuade the party that wrongfully removed or retained the child to return the child through peaceful means. If the return of the child cannot be achieved through peaceful means, a lawsuit for the return of the child should be filed. The authority that will evaluate the allegations and decide on the return of the child is the family court.⁴⁴

There is a high volume of case-law related with the Convention as Turkish citizens historically tend to form cross-border families especially within Europe. As there is a growing trend of intellectual migration towards Europe these days, number of cross-border families will continue to rise. As a matter of fact, the Convention is being effectively applied. In line with recent publications of the Hague Conference, hearing of the child is performed and the child's views are taken into consideration. In line with ECHR decisions, young age of the child doesn't in itself constitute a basis for keeping the child with his/her mother. Further, the "child objection" exception is treated sep-

⁴³ Sakarya Civil Court of Appeal, 2nd Civil Chamber, E. 2020/1140 K. 2020/878 T. 6.11.2020.

⁴⁴ Çelikel, A., Erdem, B, Milletlerarası Özel Hukuk, İstanbul, 2020, p.306.

arately than the “grave risk” exception. However, the restricted application of grave risk may be questioned in light of recent case-law examples. Unfortunately, the threshold of the grave risk exception is not as high as expected.

Summary

Turkey is a party to the Convention of 25 October 1980 on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction since 2000. The Convention has 103 State Parties. The Convention is applied widely in Turkey and there is a mass amount of case-law and doctrine. Recently, the Hague Conference issued two publications concerning the Convention. In 2020, the Guide to Good Practice on Article 13/1/b (“Guide to Good Practice”) and the Conclusions and Recommendations of the Eighth Meeting of the Special Commission (“Special Commission Report”) on the practical operation of the Convention held in October 2023. In this paper, we aimed to evaluate recent case-law of the Turkish courts concerning the Convention especially in the light of recent materials published by the Hague Conference and reached following conclusions: In line with recent publications of the Hague Conference, hearing of the child is performed and the child’s views are taken into consideration by Turkish courts. In line with ECHR decisions, young age of the child doesn’t in itself constitute a basis for keeping the child with his/her mother. Further, the “child objection” exception is treated separately than the “grave risk” exception. However, the restricted application of grave risk may be questioned in light of recent case-law examples. Unfortunately, the threshold of the grave risk exception is not as high as expected.

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